
Nanofibrous Biomaterial based Carriers and their Recent Advances in Drug and Gene Delivery

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Abstract Drug delivery by Nanofibrous biomaterials meets immense possibilities in the therapeutic area, anticipated to their structural and functional resemblance with biological Extracellular matrix (ECM). Broad spectrums of natural and polymeric materials are utilized in the fabrication of nanofibrous biomaterials. Therefore, this write-up presents considerable natural and synthetic biomaterials for the manufacturing of nanofibers with essential properties like biocompatibility and biodegradability. Various approaches with their merits and demerits in the production of nanofibrous biomaterial-based drug delivery were also described. The structural features can be individualized by the precise choice of acceptable fabrication methods, while the functional features of nanofibrous biomaterials can be ameliorated by altering the surface area. The loading and release of free drug molecules that take part in efficacy of drug delivery were also reported. This review come-up with insights into the fabrication of functional nanofibrous based carriers for effective drug delivery.

Keywords Nanofibers, Biomaterial, Polymers, Lipids, Drug delivery, Gene delivery

1. Introduction

Nanofibers are a remarkable category of biomaterials that could perhaps utilized for biomedical applications because of their specific structure and properties like high surface area [1-4], superior mechanical properties, high porosity, and low density. The main emerging application of nanofibers in recent days is the drug delivery, due to their notable structural and functional similarities with those of Extracellular Matrix (ECM). The most important characteristic feature of ideal drug delivery is a controlled amount of drug release for a definite period into the targeted site of the biological body [5-9]. This special approach of drug delivery by nanofibrous biomaterials can be achieved extensively by various polymers. Biomaterials of polymeric type are usually divided into natural (intrinsic) and synthetic polymeric biomaterials. Natural polymeric biomaterial includes chitin, gelatin, pectin, chitosan, cellulose, lignin, proteins, collagen, and pectin. These intrinsic polymers are compatible with the living tissue and hence utilized to imitate the ECM. Despite, this, it is extremely tough to the configuration the continual nanofibers. Anticipated by their special and superior properties numerous nanofibers fabrication methods have been examined and reported which include Solution blowing, Electrospinning, Self-assembly, Centrifugal spinning, and Phase separation. Of late, Electrospinning has been a solitary technique for the synthesis of nanofibers due to its various

Pros like being simplicity in apparatus, wide material option, with multifaceted and invariable morphologies. Further applications of nanofibers are also described in many research studies [10-13]. The boon and bane of such methods for the production of nanofibers in drug delivery are also being reported. Major criteria during the scheming of sustainable drug delivery are the choice of materials selected. Therefore, there is a need to comprehend properties like their physical nature, chemical appearance, morphological and surface features including the biodegradability and biocompatibility that influence the release of integrated biologically active agents. The important goal of controlled drug delivery is to achieve a sustainable dose of therapeutic agents over a given period.

2. Biomaterials for fabrication and delivery of gene systems

The drug delivery system consists of a separate reservoir for a drug adjoining the polymeric structures which regulate the release of drug delivery. Here the drug is embedded non-covalently in a fine permeable structure. Alike ABDS these reservoir-based drug delivery systems help to achieve endless drug delivery for the drugs administered into the systemic circulation [14-20]. In molecular engrave polymers are produced on a template that acts as an affinity binder. This can be explained well with cyclodextrin-based drug delivery systems, where small aquaphobic drugs are attracted to Oligosaccharide cyclodextrin where the final consequence is a complex formation that enhances the drug solubility. A familiar example of this is the study where a Heparin Binding Delivery System (HBDS) is utilized for the prolonged drug release of Basic fibroblast Growth Factor (BFGF) which in turn promotes wound healing and tissue repair. This mechanism can be achieved by the potential nature of heparin to hold together BFGF to controlled drug release [21-24]. despite fact that the long term model of ABDS embedded in severe spinal cord bruise in rats stipulated that functional recovery was not enhanced over the control group of saline following 12 weeks because of fact that wound is the consequence of backbone degradation [25-30]. It was proposed that the everlasting efficacy of the ABDS can be ameliorated by providing therapy in the chronic course when the wound is stabilized.

Figure 1: Explaining the controlled delivery systems formulated using biomaterials

3. Biomaterials for the fabrication of carriers for delivery of drug

Electrospinning is a manufacturing procedure where a voltage brings out thin natural or synthetic polymer fibers, varies from nanometer to micrometer scale in diameter [31-34]. Preparation of this polymer is achieved either by solution form at room temperature (Solution electrospinning) or by manufacture in the viscous state by providing

warmthness (melt electrospinning) [35-40]. Afterward polymer is pushed into the vent of electrical field that stabilizes over the surface tension, resulting in the droplets constantly disfigure in the flow direction, lead to nanofibers production. Such types of nanofibers are routinely utilized in reservoir based drug delivery systems that allow the amalgamation of biologically active agents [41-45]. Various benefits of electrospinning are surface flexibility, controlled drug release, and the capacity to produce different nanofibers of various morphologies [46-50]. Nanofibers produced by electron spinning have a three-dimensional permeable structure with more surface area to volume ratio resulting in substantial and promising drug delivery methods. Hydrogels possess a strong affinity towards the water and hence they can easily expand instead of liquefying in aqueous medium results in a gel-like structure. There are various approaches used in the preparation of Hydrogels [51-55]. The amount of drug release from the reservoir and its properties depend upon the choice of polymer used in the synthesis of Hydrogels. An outline of mechanisms of drug release and also ways to infuse proteins inside hydrogels [56-60]. Those are namely diffusion-controlled systems, Swelling controlled systems, chemically controlled systems, and modulated release systems. In this part, we provide restriction of hydrogels based upon their physical properties and release of biological agents like growth factors, and DNA [61-64]. This is mainly used in the specialty of neurological disorders where there is a need of delivering the numerous bioactive agents that need varied courses of drug release. Individual techniques reported here like microspheres, hydrogels, and electrospinning nanofibers are integrated to acquire such a result. Applications of such techniques are also devoid of limitations accompanied by the use of microspheres, hydrogels, and electron spinning nanofibers.

Apart from this natural polymer named silk obtained from the cocoons is also in the use of delivering the drugs. It had excellent biocompatibility and less biodegradation rate in the biological body [64-68]. A study reported the synthesis of nanofibers derived from the silk are used in the treatment of Osteoporosis and other bone-related disorders [69-72]. In vivo studies, reported biopolymers are often synthesized as fine permeable membranes. Despite this there exist demerits regarding natural biopolymers like weak tensile strength and varied structures [72-75]. Another demerit is Pharmacokinetic parameters of natural biopolymers as it is difficult to manage during the conditions of long-term drug delivery.

4. Conclusion

By stressing the merits of various drug delivery systems and their individual properties, new drug delivery systems are put forward in the area of tissue engineering. There are various perspectives and challenges in the field of controlled drug release of neurotrophic factors that must be directed for successful treatment strategies. In the specialty of nerve conduits, there is a need for the combination of different approaches like cell therapies and drug delivery systems to combat various neurological disorders. Adjusting the structural and behavioral properties in cell behavior provides different ideas in neural tissue applications. An example of notable improvement of distinction of stem cells of the murine model into neurons on PCL nanofibers in aligned topography compared to random topography. This additionally improves the separation of these cells with the concurrent use of neurotrophic factors. As explained by the results of different methods in this review, drug delivery devices are customized to make a certain sustained release of neurotrophic factors to evolve different therapies for neurological disorders.

References

- [1]. Yu, Z., Xu, Q., Dong, C., Lee, S. S., Gao, L., Li, Y., ... & Wu, J. (2015). Self-assembling peptide nanofibrous hydrogel as a versatile drug delivery platform. *Current pharmaceutical design*, 21(29), 4342-4354.
- [2]. Abdelhady, S., Honsy, K. M., & Kurakula, M. (2015). Electro Spun- Nanofibrous Mats: A Modern Wound Dressing Matrix with a Potential of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics. *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*, 10(4), 155892501501000. <https://doi.org/10.1177/155892501501000411>
- [3]. Li, W. J., Mauck, R. L., & Tuan, R. S. (2005). Electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds: production, characterization, and applications for tissue engineering and drug delivery. *Journal of Biomedical Nanotechnology*, 1(3), 259-275.

- [4]. Ahmed, O. A. A., Kurakula, M., Banjar, Z. M., Afouna, M. I., & Zidan, A. S. (2015). Quality by design coupled with near infrared in formulation of transdermal glimepiride liposomal films. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 104(6), 2062–2075. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.24448>
- [5]. Alhakamy, N. A., Ahmed, O. A. A., Kurakula, M., Caruso, G., Caraci, F., Asfour, H. Z., Alfarsi, A., Eid, B. G., Mohamed, A. I., Alruwaili, N. K., Abdulaal, W. H., Fahmy, U. A., Alhadrami, H. A., Eldakhakhny, B. M., & Abdel-Naim, A. B. (2020). Chitosan-based microparticles enhance ellagic acid's colon targeting and proapoptotic activity. *Pharmaceutics*, 12(7), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics12070652>
- [6]. Li, Z., Mei, S., Dong, Y., She, F., Li, Y., Li, P., & Kong, L. (2020). Functional Nanofibrous Biomaterials of Tailored Structures for Drug Delivery—A Critical Review. *Pharmaceutics*, 12(6), 522.
- [7]. Garg, T., Rath, G., & Goyal, A. K. (2015). Biomaterials-based nanofiber scaffold: targeted and controlled carrier for cell and drug delivery. *Journal of drug targeting*, 23(3), 202-221.
- [8]. Alhakamy, N. A., Fahmy, U. A., Ahmed, O. A. A., Caruso, G., Caraci, F., Asfour, H. Z., Bakhrebah, M. A., Alomary, M. N., Abdulaal, W. H., Okbazghi, S. Z., Abdel-Naim, A. B., Eid, B. G., Aldawsari, H. M., Kurakula, M., & Mohamed, A. I. (2020). Chitosan coated microparticles enhance simvastatin colon targeting and pro-apoptotic activity. *Marine Drugs*, 18(4), 226. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md18040226>
- [9]. Yao, Q., Liu, Y., Selvaratnam, B., Koodali, R. T., & Sun, H. (2018). Mesoporous silicate nanoparticles/3D nanofibrous scaffold-mediated dual-drug delivery for bone tissue engineering. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 279, 69-78.
- [10]. Hasnain, M. S., Kiran, V., Kurakula, M., Rao, G. K., Tabish, M., & Nayak, A. K. (2020). Use of alginates for drug delivery in dentistry. In *Alginates in Drug Delivery* (pp. 387–404). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-817640-5.00015-7>
- [11]. He, C., Nie, W., & Feng, W. (2014). Engineering of biomimetic nanofibrous matrices for drug delivery and tissue engineering. *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, 2(45), 7828-7848.
- [12]. Hasnain, M. S., Nayak, A. K., Kurakula, M., & Hoda, M. N. (2020). Alginate nanoparticles in drug delivery. In *Alginates in Drug Delivery* (pp. 129–152). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-817640-5.00006-6>
- [13]. Ji, W., Yang, F., Seyednejad, H., Chen, Z., Hennink, W. E., Anderson, J. M., ... & Jansen, J. A. (2012). Biocompatibility and degradation characteristics of PLGA-based electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds with nanoapatite incorporation. *Biomaterials*, 33(28), 6604-6614.
- [14]. Hosny, K. M., Aldawsari, H. M., Bahmdan, R. H., Sindi, A. M., Kurakula, M., Alrobaian, M. M., Aldryhim, A. Y., Alkhalidi, H. M., Bahmdan, H. H., Khallaf, R. A., & El Sisi, A. M. (2019). Preparation, Optimization, and Evaluation of Hyaluronic Acid-Based Hydrogel Loaded with Miconazole Self-Nanoemulsion for the Treatment of Oral Thrush. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, 20(7), 297. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-019-1496-7>
- [15]. Liu, X., Jin, X., & Ma, P. X. (2011). Nanofibrous hollow microspheres self-assembled from star-shaped polymers as injectable cell carriers for knee repair. *Nature materials*, 10(5), 398-406.
- [16]. Kurakula, M., & A. Ahmed, T. (2015). Co-Delivery of Atorvastatin Nanocrystals in PLGA based in situ Gel for Anti-Hyperlipidemic Efficacy. *Current Drug Delivery*, 13(2), 211–220. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1567201813666151109102718>
- [17]. Lu, Q., Wang, X., Lu, S., Li, M., Kaplan, D. L., & Zhu, H. (2011). Nanofibrous architecture of silk fibroin scaffolds prepared with a mild self-assembly process. *Biomaterials*, 32(4), 1059-1067.
- [18]. Kurakula, M., Ahmed, O. A. A., Fahmy, U. A., & Ahmed, T. A. (2016). Solid lipid nanoparticles for transdermal delivery of avanafil: optimization, formulation, in-vitro and ex-vivo studies. *Journal of Liposome Research*, 26(4), 288–296. <https://doi.org/10.3109/08982104.2015.1117490>
- [19]. Liang, D., Hsiao, B. S., & Chu, B. (2007). Functional electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds for biomedical applications. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*, 59(14), 1392-1412.
- [20]. Kurakula, M., El-Helw, A. M., Sobahi, T. R., & Abdelaal, M. Y. (2015). Chitosan based atorvastatin

- nanocrystals: Effect of cationic charge on particle size, formulation stability, and in-vivo efficacy. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 10, 321–334. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S77731>
- [21]. Shin, M., Yoshimoto, H., & Vacanti, J. P. (2004). In vivo bone tissue engineering using mesenchymal stem cells on a novel electrospun nanofibrous scaffold. *Tissue engineering*, 10(1-2), 33-41.
- [22]. Shi, Y., Li, Y., Wu, J., Wang, W., Dong, A., & Zhang, J. (2014). A novel transdermal drug delivery system based on self-adhesive Janus nanofibrous film with high breathability and monodirectional water-penetration. *Journal of Biomaterials Science, Polymer Edition*, 25(7), 713-728.
- [23]. Kurakula, M., & Koteswara Rao, G. S. N. (2020). Moving polyvinyl pyrrolidone electrospun nanofibers and bioprinted scaffolds toward multidisciplinary biomedical applications. *European Polymer Journal*, 136, 109919. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2020.109919>
- [24]. Namdari, M., & Eatemadi, A. (2016). Nanofibrous bioengineered heart valve—application in paediatric medicine. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 84, 1179-1188.
- [25]. Miszuk, J. M., Hu, J., & Sun, H. (2020). Biomimetic Nanofibrous 3D Materials for Craniofacial Bone Tissue Engineering. *ACS Applied Bio Materials*, 3(10), 6538-6545.
- [26]. Kurakula, M., Naveen, N. R., & Yadav, K. S. (2020). Formulations for Polymer Coatings. *Polymer Coatings*, 415–443. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119655145.ch19>
- [27]. Monteiro, N., Ribeiro, D., Martins, A., Faria, S., Fonseca, N. A., Moreira, J. N., ... & Neves, N. M. (2014). Instructive nanofibrous scaffold comprising runt-related transcription factor 2 gene delivery for bone tissue engineering. *ACS Nano*, 8(8), 8082-8094.
- [28]. Kurakula, M., & Raghavendra Naveen, N. (2020). In situ gel loaded with chitosan-coated simvastatin nanoparticles: Promising delivery for effective anti-proliferative activity against tongue carcinoma. *Marine Drugs*, 18(4), 201. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md18040201>
- [29]. Kim, H. S., & Yoo, H. S. (2010). MMPs-responsive release of DNA from electrospun nanofibrous matrix for local gene therapy: in vitro and in vivo evaluation. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 145(3), 264-271.
- [30]. Liang, Y., & Kiick, K. L. (2014). Heparin-functionalized polymeric biomaterials in tissue engineering and drug delivery applications. *Acta biomaterialia*, 10(4), 1588-1600.
- [31]. Kurakula, M., Rao, G. K., Kiran, V., Hasnain, M. S., & Nayak, A. K. (2020). Alginate-based hydrogel systems for drug releasing in wound healing. In *Alginates in Drug Delivery* (pp. 323–358). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-817640-5.00013-3>
- [32]. Xi, Y., Ge, J., Guo, Y., Lei, B., & Ma, P. X. (2018). Biomimetic elastomeric polypeptide-based nanofibrous matrix for overcoming multidrug-resistant bacteria and enhancing full-thickness wound healing/skin regeneration. *ACS nano*, 12(11), 10772-10784.
- [33]. Rao, G. S. N. K., Kurakula, M., & Yadav, K. S. (2020). Application of Electrospun Materials in Gene Delivery. *Electrospun Materials and Their Allied Applications*, 265–306
- [34]. Feng, G., Zhang, Z., Dang, M., Zhang, X., Doleyres, Y., Song, Y., ... & Ma, P. X. (2017). Injectable nanofibrous spongy microspheres for NR4A1 plasmid DNA transfection to reverse fibrotic degeneration and support disc regeneration. *Biomaterials*, 131, 86-97.
- [35]. Holzwarth, J. M., & Ma, P. X. (2011). Biomimetic nanofibrous scaffolds for bone tissue engineering. *Biomaterials*, 32(36), 9622-9629.
- [36]. Kurakula, M., & Rao, G. S. N. K. (2020). Pharmaceutical assessment of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP): As excipient from conventional to controlled delivery systems with a spotlight on COVID-19 inhibition. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*, 60, 102046. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2020.102046>
- [37]. Hakkarainen, E., Kõrkjas, A., Laidmäe, I., Lust, A., Semjonov, K., Kogermann, K., ... & Heinämäki, J. (2019). Comparison of traditional and ultrasound-enhanced electrospinning in fabricating nanofibrous drug delivery systems. *Pharmaceutics*, 11(10), 495.
- [38]. Kurakula, M., Sobahi, T. R., El-Helw, A., & Abdelaal, M. Y. (2014). Development and validation of a RP-HPLC method for assay of atorvastatin and its application in dissolution studies on thermosensitive hydrogel-based nanocrystals. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 13(10), 1681–1687.

- <https://doi.org/10.4314/tjpr.v13i10.16>
- [39]. Bagó, J. R., Pegna, G. J., Okolie, O., Mohiti-Asli, M., Lobo, E. G., & Hingtgen, S. D. (2016). Electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds increase the efficacy of stem cell-mediated therapy of surgically resected glioblastoma. *Biomaterials*, 90, 116-125.
- [40]. Dash, T. K., & Konkimalla, V. B. (2012). Poly-ε-caprolactone based formulations for drug delivery and tissue engineering: A review. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 158(1), 15-33.
- [41]. Kurakula, M., Srinivas, C., Kasturi, N., & Diwan, P. V. (2012). Formulation and Evaluation of Prednisolone Proliposomal Gel for Effective Topical Pharmacotherapy. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Drug Research*, 4(1), 35. www.ijpsdr.com
- [42]. Bacakova, L., Bacakova, M., Pajorova, J., Kudlackova, R., Stankova, L., Filova, E., ... & Kromka, A. (2016). Nanofibrous scaffolds as promising cell carriers for tissue engineering. *Nanofiber Research-Reaching New Heights*, 29-53.
- [43]. Hinderer, S., Layland, S. L., & Schenke-Layland, K. (2016). ECM and ECM-like materials—biomaterials for applications in regenerative medicine and cancer therapy. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*, 97, 260-269.
- [44]. Mallesh, K., Pasula, N., & Kumar Ranjith, C. P. (2012). Piroxicam proliposomal gel: a novel approach for tropical delivery. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*, 5(3), 1755–1763.
- [45]. Kurakula M, Mohd AB, Rao PA, Diwan PV. Estimation of piroxicam in proliposomal formulation using RP HPLC method. *Int. J. Chem. Anal. Sci.* 2011; 2: 1193. 2011; 1196.
- [46]. Kurakula M, Naveen NR. Prospection of recent chitosan biomedical trends: Evidence from patent analysis (2009–2020). *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2020 Oct 15.
- [47]. Sun, J., & Tan, H. (2013). Alginate-based biomaterials for regenerative medicine applications. *Materials*, 6(4), 1285-1309.
- [48]. Venkatesh, M., & Mallesh, K. (2013). Self-Nano Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (Snedds) for Oral Delivery of Atorvastatin- Formulation and Bioavailability Studies. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 3(3), 131–140. <https://doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v3i3.517>
- [49]. Lee, S., Kim, J. S., Chu, H. S., Kim, G. W., Won, J. I., & Jang, J. H. (2011). Electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds for controlled release of adeno-associated viral vectors. *Acta Biomaterialia*, 7(11), 3868-3876.
- [50]. Kurakula M, Mohd AB, Samhuidrom AP, Diwan PV. Estimation of prednisolone in proliposomal formulation using RP HPLC method. *Int. J. Res. Pharm. Biomed. Sci.* 2011; 2: 663. 2011;1669.
- [51]. Ma, Z., Kotaki, M., Inai, R., & Ramakrishna, S. (2005). Potential of nanofiber matrix as tissue-engineering scaffolds. *Tissue engineering*, 11(1-2), 101-109.
- [52]. Chan, O. C. M., So, K. F., & Chan, B. P. (2008). Fabrication of nano-fibrous collagen microspheres for protein delivery and effects of photochemical crosslinking on release kinetics. *Journal of Controlled Release*, 129(2), 135-143.
- [53]. Murali, V. P., Fujiwara, T., Gallop, C., Wang, Y., Wilson, J. A., Atwill, M. T., Kurakula, M., & Bumgardner, J. D. (2020). Modified electrospun chitosan membranes for controlled release of simvastatin. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 584, 119438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2020.119438>
- [54]. Feng, Z. Q., Chu, X., Huang, N. P., Wang, T., Wang, Y., Shi, X., ... & Gu, Z. Z. (2009). The effect of nanofibrous galactosylated chitosan scaffolds on the formation of rat primary hepatocyte aggregates and the maintenance of liver function. *Biomaterials*, 30(14), 2753-2763.
- [55]. Naveen, N., Kumar, R., Balaji, S., Uma, T. S., Natrajan, T. S., & Sehgal, P. K. (2010). Synthesis of nonwoven nanofibers by electrospinning—a promising biomaterial for tissue engineering and drug delivery. *Advanced Engineering Materials*, 12(8), B380-B387.
- [56]. Kalmer, R. R., Mohammadi, M., Najafpour, G., Golizadeh, M., Haghghatnia, Y., & Karimi, A. (2020). Fabrication of multifunctional microfibrillar and nanofibrillar cellulose carriers and comparison of cell adhesion and spreading potential on them. *Biointerface Research in Applied Chemistry*, 10(3), 5387-5391.
- [57]. Abdul Khalil, H. P. S., Adnan, A. S., Yahya, E. B., Olaiya, N. G., Safrida, S., Hossain, M., ... & Pasquini,

- D. (2020). A Review on plant cellulose nanofibre-based aerogels for biomedical applications. *Polymers*, 12(8), 1759.
- [58]. Naguib, Ghada Hussein, Al-Hazmi, F. E., Kurakula, M., Abdulaziz Al-Dharrab, A., Mohamed Hosny, K., Mohammed Alkhalidi, H., Tharwat Hamed, M., Habiballah Hassan, A., Al-Mohammadi, A. M., Mohamed Alnowaiser, A., & Henry Pashley, D. (2018). Zein coated zinc oxide nanoparticles: Fabrication and antimicrobial evaluation as dental aid. *International Journal of Pharmacology*, 14(8), 1051–1059. <https://doi.org/10.3923/ijp.2018.1051.1059>
- [59]. Pilehvar-Soltanahmadi, Y., Dadashpour, M., Mohajeri, A., Fattahi, A., Sheervalilou, R., & Zarghami, N. (2018). An overview on application of natural substances incorporated with electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds to development of innovative wound dressings. *Mini reviews in medicinal chemistry*, 18(5), 414-427.
- [60]. Jemni-Damer, N., Guedan-Duran, A., Fuentes-Andion, M., Serrano-Bengoechea, N., Alfageme-Lopez, N., Armada-Maresca, F., ... & Kaplan, D. L. (2020). Biotechnology and Biomaterial-Based Therapeutic Strategies for Age-Related Macular Degeneration. Part I: Biomaterials-Based Drug Delivery Devices. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 8, 1257.
- [61]. Gupte, M. J., & Ma, P. X. (2012). Nanofibrous scaffolds for dental and craniofacial applications. *Journal of dental research*, 91(3), 227-234.
- [62]. Naveen, N. R., Gopinath, C., & Kurakula, M. (2020). Okra-thioglycolic acid conjugate-synthesis, characterization, and evaluation as a mucoadhesive polymer. *Processes*, 8(3), 316. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr8030316>
- [63]. Goldberg, M., Langer, R., & Jia, X. (2007). Nanostructured materials for applications in drug delivery and tissue engineering. *Journal of Biomaterials Science, Polymer Edition*, 18(3), 241-268.
- [64]. Jayarama Reddy, V., Radhakrishnan, S., Ravichandran, R., Mukherjee, S., Balamurugan, R., Sundarajan, S., & Ramakrishna, S. (2013). Nanofibrous structured biomimetic strategies for skin tissue regeneration. *Wound Repair and regeneration*, 21(1), 1-16.
- [65]. Raghavendra Naveen, N., Kurakula, M., & Gowthami, B. (2020). Process optimization by response surface methodology for preparation and evaluation of methotrexate loaded chitosan nanoparticles. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.01.491>
- [66]. Jayarama Reddy, V., Radhakrishnan, S., Ravichandran, R., Mukherjee, S., Balamurugan, R., Sundarajan, S., & Ramakrishna, S. (2013). Nanofibrous structured biomimetic strategies for skin tissue regeneration. *Wound Repair and regeneration*, 21(1), 1-16.
- [67]. Ingavle, G. C., & Leach, J. K. (2014). Advancements in electrospinning of polymeric nanofibrous scaffolds for tissue engineering. *Tissue Engineering Part B: Reviews*, 20(4), 277-293.
- [68]. Vanitasagar, S., Srinivas, C., Subhashini, N. J. P., & Mallesh, K. (2012). Solid dispersion-a comparative study on the dissolution rate of aceclofenac. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4(SUPPL.3), 274–278.
- [69]. Zhong, W., Xing, M. M., & Maibach, H. I. (2010). Nanofibrous materials for wound care. *Cutaneous and ocular toxicology*, 29(3), 143-152.
- [70]. Hosny KM, Alhakamy NA, Almodhwahi MA, Kurakula M, Almeahmady AM, Elgebaly SS. Self-Nanoemulsifying System Loaded with Sildenafil Citrate and Incorporated within Oral Lyophilized Flash Tablets: Preparation, Optimization, and In Vivo Evaluation. *Pharmaceutics*. 2020 Nov;12(11):1124.
- [71]. Prabakaran, M., Jayakumar, R., & Nair, S. V. (2011). Electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds-current status and prospects in drug delivery. In *Biomedical applications of polymeric nanofibers* (pp. 241-262). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [72]. Modica de Mohac, L., Keating, A. V., de Fátima Pina, M., & Raimi-Abraham, B. T. (2019). Engineering of nanofibrous amorphous and crystalline solid dispersions for oral drug delivery. *Pharmaceutics*, 11(1), 7.
- [73]. Kurakula M, Rao GK. Probiotics in Lung Cancer: An Emerging Field of Multifarious Potential and Opportunities. In *Probiotic Research in Therapeutics* (pp. 125-158). Springer, Singapore.

- [74]. Yu, Z., Xu, Q., Dong, C., Lee, S. S., Gao, L., Li, Y., ... & Wu, J. (2015). Self-assembling peptide nanofibrous hydrogel as a versatile drug delivery platform. *Current pharmaceutical design*, 21(29), 4342-4354.
- [75]. Li, W. J., Mauck, R. L., & Tuan, R. S. (2005). Electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds: production, characterization, and applications for tissue engineering and drug delivery. *Journal of Biomedical Nanotechnology*, 1(3), 259-275.

